

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of zinc and cadmium ions with some nitrogen and sulphur donors

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Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of zinc and cadmium ions with sulphur ligand, 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate [$i\text{-MNT}^{2-} = \{\text{S}_2\text{C} : \text{C}(\text{CN})_2\}^{2-}$] as a primary ligand and nitrogen donor, *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD), as secondary ligand of the composition $\text{M}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ [$\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II}] have been synthesized. Reactions of $\text{M}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ with pyridine bases such as pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic) have been carried out under different reaction conditions. Some of the reactions have yielded addition compounds whereas others have resulted the compounds in which OPD has been replaced by pyridine bases. The complexes have been characterized on the basis of analytical data, molar conductance, infrared and NMR spectral studies. The molar conductance data reveal that all of the complexes have non-electrolytic nature in DMF solution. Infrared spectral studies suggest bidentate chelating behaviour of $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ion and OPD while other ligands show unidentate behaviour in its complexes.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complex, cadmium, zinc.

Introduction

A variety of dithiolate ligands have been used to synthesize transition as well as non-transition metal complexes to study their coordination behaviours. Thus the coordination chemistry of metal dithiolates has been area of interest for several years^{1,2}. Recently the role of dithioligands have been explored in the design of many electrically conducting molecular solids³⁻⁶. The interest in this area stems from various reasons such as stabilization of transition metal ions in its unusual oxidation states, facile redox behaviour, stabilization of square planar geometry around transition metal ions, interesting spectral and magnetic properties. In addition, metal dithiolates have a number of industrial and biological applications^{2,7}.

Among 1,1-dithioligands, 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate ion shows exciting coordination properties by virtue of its chelating and bridging behaviour which have been found in its binary, ternary and heterobimetallic complexes^{2,8-10}. Our earlier communications¹¹⁻¹⁴ include the studies on mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate and some nitrogen containing bases such as ammonia, ethylenediamine, pyridine, 2,2-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline. Prior to our report, McClevery *et al.*¹⁵ have obtained and characterized a series of mixed 1,1- and 1,2-dithiolate complexes of cobalt and iron. From our laboratory, mixed

ligand complexes of nickel(II) with 1,1-dithiolate and nitrogen donors have been reported^{16,17}.

In continuation of our work, synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of zinc and cadmium ions with potassium 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate ($\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$) and primary aromatic diamine (*o*-phenylenediamine, OPD) and/or heterocyclic tertiary monoamine were, therefore, undertaken and the results of our investigations are reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

The analytical data and stoichiometries of the mixed ligand complexes derived from *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD) and 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate ion ($i\text{-MNT}$) suggest the composition $\text{M}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ [$\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II}]. The reaction products of $[\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})]$ with pyridine bases have the compositions, $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})\text{L}_2$ [$\text{L} = \text{pyridine (py)}$, α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic)] and $[\text{Zn}(\text{py})_2(i\text{-MNT})]$. The complex, $[\text{Zn}(\text{py})_2(i\text{-MNT})]$ is a substitution product of $[\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})]$ in which OPD is replaced by pyridine molecules suggesting the strained structure around Zn^{II} ion in $[\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})]$ complex. On the other hand, reaction of $[\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})]$ with pyridine bases have resulted complexes of the compositions, $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})\text{L}_x$ [$\text{L} = \text{py}$, $x = 2$; α -pic, $x = 1$] and $\text{CdL}_2(i\text{-MNT})$.

MNT) [L = β -pic or γ -pic]. The complexes are almost insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO, giving coloured solutions.

The decomposition temperatures for complexes lie in the range 144–258 °C. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF solutions fall in the region 2.9–38.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which are consistent with non-electrolytic nature¹⁸.

Infrared spectral studies :

The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes have been interpreted in the light of earlier investigations^{1,10,19–23} on transition and non-transition metal isomaleonitrile dithiolates (1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolates). The i-MNT²⁻ ligand ion may be described by resonating structures in its complexes as shown in Fig. 1.

Each of the moieties in the complexes undergoes particular vibrations and contributes certain peaks to their IR spectra. The electron delocalization in the chelated i-MNT²⁻ ring leads to the coupling of vibrational modes so that few bands in IR spectra represent pure vibrations. The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes display characteristic stretching frequencies associated with C \equiv N, C=C, C-S and M-S from i-MNT²⁻; aryl ring vibrations with metal heterocyclic nitrogen vibrations from py, α -pic, β -pic and γ -pic and amine vibrations with metal-amine nitrogen vibrations from OPD.

Fig. 1

The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band appearing at 2195 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 2200 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_2\text{i-MNT}$, is observed in the range 2189–2211 cm^{-1} in the mixed ligand complexes. In most of the complexes definite splitting of this peak is observed which reflects a lower symmetry for these complexes. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ absorption in all the complexes appears in the range 1367–1404 cm^{-1} is close to that observed in free $\text{K}_2\text{i-MNT}$ ligand (1360 cm^{-1}), which implies some delocalization of π -electron out of the C=C bond. The positive shifts observed in stretching frequencies of C \equiv N and C=C suggest that resonance form (a) (Fig. 1) is more dominant in these complexes of i-MNT²⁻ ligand ion. A band at 960 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 985 cm^{-1} on the higher frequency side is observed in the IR spectrum of $\text{K}_2\text{i-MNT}$ due to =CS₂ group. The corresponding band and shoulder in the mixed ligand complexes are found in the range 942–970 and 963–982 cm^{-1} respectively. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ band occurring in the spectrum of $\text{K}_2\text{i-MNT}$ at 860 cm^{-1} appears as a single band in the range 865–889 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating symmetrical bonding of both the sulphur atoms to metal ions. Similar bonding behaviour of i-MNT²⁻ ion is reported²¹ in $\text{K}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{i-MNT})_2]$ where a single $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ band is observed at 900 cm^{-1} .

The mixed ligand complexes containing heterocyclic nitrogen donors show in-plane ring and out-of-plane ring deformation bands in the ranges 618–658 and 421–435 cm^{-1} respectively indicating coordination through nitrogen atom. Complexes containing *o*-phenylenediamine ligand exhibit a group of broad band in the range 3119–3346 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ (asymmetric and symmetric) stretching modes lower than the free *o*-phenylenediamine ligand bands (3188–3383 cm^{-1}). The N-H bending (scissoring) vibration mode is observed in the range 1602–1624 cm^{-1} for the complexes which is lower than the free *o*-phenylenediamine band (1633 cm^{-1}). These shifts towards the lower frequency clearly suggest the amino nitrogen coordination to metal ion. Aromatic, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ for the aromatic ligands in these complexes show a weak intensity band in the region 3014–3110 cm^{-1} . Methyl, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ for complexes containing α -pic, β -pic and γ -pic, ligands show a band in the region 2850–2970 cm^{-1} . A strong absorption band observed in the range 704–799 cm^{-1} in these complexes is attributed to out-of-plane =C-H ring (aromatic) bending mode which is found in free OPD at 751 cm^{-1} , characteristic of substituted benzene. Very weak combination and overtone bands appear in the 1650–2000 cm^{-1} region in complexes, and the number and relative positions of these bands are remarkably

for *ortho* disubstituted benzenoid structure.

The non-ligand bands observed in the ranges 310–380 and 250–310 cm^{-1} in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})^{19}$ and $\nu(\text{M-S})^{22}$ modes respectively.

^1H NMR spectra :

^1H NMR spectra of two representative complexes, $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$, were recorded to get structural information. The free *o*-phenylenediamine ligand shows two NMR signals at δ 3.35(s) ppm and δ 6.71(m) ppm for amino protons and aromatic -CH protons respectively. The complex, $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$, shows two NMR signals at δ 4.41(s) ppm and δ 6.47(m) ppm corresponding to amino protons and aromatic -CH protons while $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ shows the corresponding NMR signals at δ 4.39(s) ppm and δ 6.48(m) ppm. The amino protons signal shifts downfield in the spectra of complexes due to the formation of a coordinate linkage between nitrogen and metal ion while aromatic -CH protons signal shifts upfield suggesting shielding which probably arises due to donation of lone pair of electrons of

amino groups to metal ions.

Reactivity of the complex :

When $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ was reacted with heterocyclic nitrogen bases, py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic, under different reaction conditions then it yielded addition and substitution products of the compositions $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})\text{L}_2$ [L = py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic] and $\text{Zn}(\text{py})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ respectively. On the other hand, $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ was allowed to react with heterocyclic nitrogen bases, py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic, under different reaction conditions addition as well as substitution products of the compositions $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})\text{L}_x$ [L = py, $x = 2$; α -pic, $x = 1$] and $\text{CdL}_2(i\text{-MNT})$ [L = β -pic or γ -pic] respectively. The results suggest that Zn^{II} ion in $\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ complex can easily extend its coordination number irrespective of nature of heterocyclic bases while Cd^{II} ion in $\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ can only extend its coordination number with pyridine or α -picoline. The substitution products are obtained after replacing bidentate chelating ligand (OPD) by monodentate heterocyclic nitrogen donors suggesting strained structure for the reacting species which is relaxed in substitution products.

Table 1. Analytical data and molar conductance of the mixed ligand complexes

Complex (Colour)	% Yield (Dec. temp. °C)	Found (Calcd.) %					Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) (in DMF)
		Zn/Cd	S	N	C	H	
$\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ (Light yellow)	70 (214)	20.70 (20.84)	20.52 (20.44)	16.90 (17.86)	36.98 (38.28)	2.21 (2.57)	38.00
$\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\text{py})_2$ (Grey)	50 (144)	13.98 (13.85)	13.69 (13.58)	16.62 (17.80)	50.34 (50.90)	3.53 (3.84)	24.00
$\text{Zn}(\text{py})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ (Yellowish white)	35 (250)	17.56 (17.97)	17.68 (17.62)	15.01 (15.40)	45.68 (46.22)	2.35 (2.77)	34.00
$\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\alpha\text{-pic})_2$ (Brown)	65 (158)	12.82 (13.07)	12.75 (12.82)	16.42 (16.80)	52.43 (52.85)	4.12 (4.43)	32.00
$\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\beta\text{-pic})_2$ (Yellow)	40 (190)	12.98 (13.08)	12.87 (12.82)	16.52 (16.80)	52.34 (52.85)	4.01 (4.43)	31.00
$\text{Zn}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\gamma\text{-pic})_2$ (Brown)	75 (128)	12.85 (13.07)	12.65 (12.82)	16.21 (16.80)	52.35 (52.85)	4.11 (4.43)	20.00
$\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})$ (Light yellow)	75 (226)	30.76 (31.15)	17.32 (17.77)	15.01 (15.53)	32.98 (33.29)	1.82 (2.23)	9.01
$\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\text{py})_2$ (Grey)	80 (202)	21.46 (21.66)	12.20 (12.35)	15.76 (16.29)	45.89 (46.29)	3.12 (3.49)	10.00
$\text{Cd}(\text{OPD})(i\text{-MNT})(\alpha\text{-pic})$ (Yellowish grey)	65 (224)	24.67 (24.76)	14.22 (14.12)	14.88 (15.43)	41.97 (42.34)	3.12 (3.35)	10.30
$\text{Cd}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ (Yellow)	70 (258)	24.98 (25.61)	14.21 (14.61)	12.25 (12.76)	43.32 (43.79)	3.11 (3.21)	2.90
$\text{Cd}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ (Dirty white)	70 (250)	25.32 (25.61)	14.32 (14.61)	12.43 (12.76)	43.62 (43.79)	3.11 (3.21)	9.70

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used in this study were obtained from E. Merck of G.R. grade or equivalent quality. α -, β - and γ -picolines were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company. K_2i -MNT. H_2O was prepared by a known literature procedure²⁴. The complexes were analyzed for metals using standard literature procedures²⁵. Sulphur was estimated as $BaSO_4$ gravimetrically. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined micro-analytically. The molar conductance of the millimolar solutions of the complexes in DMF was measured using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 304 with a dip-type cell with platinized electrodes. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol (4000 – 200 cm^{-1}) and in KBr pellets (4000 – 400 cm^{-1}) on a Bomem DA-8 FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded for free ligand (OPD) in $CDCl_3$ and complexes in $DMSO-d_6$ solution on Bruker Advance DRX 300 FT-NMR spectrophotometer. Analytical data together with colour, decomposition temperatures and molar conductance values are presented in Table 1. Important infrared spectral data are given in Table 2.

Synthesis of the complexes :

$M(OPD)(i-MNT)$ [$M = Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II}]: 20 mL Methanolic solution containing 5 mM of *o*-phenylenediamine was added slowly with stirring to a 20 mL methanolic solution containing 5 mM hydrated metal nitrate which resulted yellowish flocculent and white silky precipitate with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions respectively. To this resulting mixture, 40 mL water was added slowly with stirring which made the precipitate almost soluble and finally filtered. To this

filtered solution, 20 mL aqueous solution having 5 mM of K_2i -MNT. H_2O was added with stirring which yielded light yellow precipitates after 10 min of stirring in case of Zn^{II} and simultaneously with Cd^{II} . The mixture were further stirred for half an hour for completion of reaction and suction filtered. The precipitates were washed successively with water, methanol, ether and dried *in vacuo* over $CaCl_2$.

$Zn(py)_2(i-MNT)$: 5 mM of $Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)$ was dissolved in 30 mL of pyridine by adding slowly with stirring and just after a few seconds a light yellowish white microcrystalline precipitate was obtained. The mixture was stirred further half an hour to ensure the completion of the reaction. The precipitate was filtered, washed first with pyridine and then finally with ether till the washings were colourless and dried in open air.

$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)(py)_2$: 5 mM of $Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)$ was dissolved in 30 mL of pyridine with stirring and the light yellowish precipitate obtained was removed by filtration. The filtrate after 15 days yielded grey coloured precipitate which was washed with ether till the washing liquid remained colourless and dried in open air.

$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)L_2$ [$L = \alpha$ -, β - or γ -picoline] : 5 mM of $Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)$ was dissolved in 15 mL of α -picoline, 40 mL of β -picoline or 25 mL of γ -picoline with vigorous stirring as to the solubility of the starting material is different in these bases. The colour of solution became reddish yellow. On standing the solution of $Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)$ in β -picoline yielded light yellow precipitate after one day while the solution in α -picoline yielded brown coloured precipitate after four days. The

Table 2. Characteristic IR bands (cm^{-1}) for the mixed ligand complexes

Complex	$\nu(C\equiv N)$	$\nu(C=C)$	$\nu(=CS_2)$	$\nu(C-S)$	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu(M-S)$
$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)$	2205vs	1398vs	957s, 975sh	870s	380m	310m
$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)(py)_2$	2195sh, 2181vs	1377m	965s, 979sh	880s	370m	300m
$Zn(py)_2(i-MNT)$	2205vs	1404vs	961vs, 982sh	865s	380m	305m
$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)(\alpha\text{-pic})_2$	2202vs	1385vs	945s, 981sh	878s	375m	270m
$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)(\beta\text{-pic})_2$	2189vs	1358vs, 1371vs	947s, 976sh	876s	350m	275m
$Zn(OPD)(i-MNT)(\gamma\text{-pic})_2$	2197vs	1379s	942s, 970sh	876s	355m	263m
$Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)$	2201vs	1375vs	945s, 963s	876s	340m	260m
$Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(py)_2$	2211vs	1376vs	947s, 970sh	878s	320m	250m
$Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(\alpha\text{-pic})$	2203vs	1376vs	945s, 963sh	876s	310m	255m
$Cd(\beta\text{-pic})_2(i-MNT)$	2209vs	1389w	970s, 982sh	889s	325m	270m
$Cd(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(i-MNT)$	2206vs	1389vs	943s	875s	330m	275m

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, sh = shoulder.

precipitates were washed with ether several times till the filtrate remained colourless and dried in open air. On the other hand solution in γ -picoline yielded sticky black polymeric type of material after one month. This was washed with ether several times after crushing the sticky precipitate with glass rod which finally yielded non-sticky brown coloured precipitate and was dried in open air.

$Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(py)_2$: 5 mM of Cd(OPD)(i-MNT) was added slowly with vigorous shaking to 10 mL of pyridine. The mixture remained turbid for some time and finally dissolves giving clear solution. The colour of solution changes from light yellow to brown as the concentration of Cd(OPD)(i-MNT) increases. The solution was finally stirred for half an hour but no precipitate was found. On standing the solution yielded little micro-crystalline precipitate on next day. The mixture was left for further precipitation. After one month the solution became dry and yielded grey coloured precipitate sticking to the surface of the beaker. The precipitate was washed with ether several times with glass rod scratching. This yielded non-sticky grey coloured micro-crystalline precipitate.

$Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(\alpha-pic)$: 3 mM of Cd(OPD)(i-MNT) was added gradually to 15 mL of α -picoline with stirring which remains turbid for some time but finally dissolves. On prolonged stirring little precipitate appeared. The mixture was kept for complete precipitation. After about one month the solution became dry and yielded black sticky material. The black sticky material was washed with ether for several times after crushing the precipitate with glass rod which finally yielded non-sticky yellowish grey precipitate and was dried in open air.

$Cd(\beta-pic)_2(i-MNT)$: 3 mM of Cd(OPD)(i-MNT) was added gradually to 25 mL of β -picoline with stirring for dissolution but some precipitate remained undissolved. To this suspension 35 mL of dimethylformamide (DMF) was added slowly with stirring which resulted yellow coloured solution. The solution was kept under observation and no precipitation took place even after five days while colour of solution changed from deep yellow to brown. To this solution water (35 mL) was added slowly with stirring till the solution became just turbid and on further stirring yielded yellow micro-crystalline precipitate which was suction filtered and washed with water, alcohol and ether successively. It was dried in open air.

$Cd(\gamma-pic)_2(i-MNT)$: 3 mM of Cd(OPD)(i-MNT) was dissolved completely in 10 mL of γ -picoline with vigorous shaking which gave deep yellow coloured solution.

On prolonged shaking it did not yield any precipitate under normal atmospheric condition. After one month the solution became dry and yielded dark coloured micro-crystalline sticky material. The precipitate was washed with ether several times after crushing it with glass rod which finally yielded non-sticky dirty white coloured precipitate. The precipitate was dried in open air.

Conclusions :

Based on stoichiometries and spectrochemical studies tetrahedral structures for Zn(OPD)(i-MNT), Zn(py)₂(i-MNT), Cd(OPD)(i-MNT), Cd(β -pic/ γ -pic)₂(i-MNT) and octahedral structures for rest of the complexes except Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(α -pic) have been proposed. In the complex Cd(OPD)(i-MNT)(α -pic), Cd^{II} ion is penta-coordinated and it may have distorted square pyramidal structure.

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